

P25 Fatty acid composition of erythrocytes in multiple organ dysfunction syndrome

A Osipenko¹, A Marochkov²
¹A. Kuleshov Mogilev State University, Mogilev, Belarus; ²Mogilev Regional Hospital, Mogilev, Belarus
Critical Care 2015, 19(Suppl 1):P25 (doi: 10.1186/cc14105)

Introduction Change in fatty acid composition of erythrocytes and blood plasma in cases of various pathological conditions is evidence of lipid metabolism disorder and can indicate the reasons for and the degree of these disorders [1]. The aim of this study was to assess the FA composition of plasma and erythrocytes in patients with multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS).

Methods The objects of study were 19 people with MODS (37.6 ± 8.3 years) of various etiologies. The blood of 17 healthy volunteers aged 38.4 ± 3.3 years served as control. The FA analysis was conducted using capillary gas-liquid chromatography. Quantitative evaluation of individual FA content was made as a mass percentage of their total ($C_{14:0}$ to $C_{22:6}$). Statistical analysis was performed using the Mann-Whitney *U* test ($P < 0.05$).

Results Our data indicate that changes in blood plasma FA composition in patients with MODS are mainly caused by activation of lipolysis in fat depots and are accompanied by an increase of monounsaturated fatty acids, a decrease in saturated stearic acid and polyunsaturated fatty acids in the ratio. In conditions of increased level of monounsaturated palmitoleic ($C_{16:1}$) and oleic ($C_{18:1}$) FA in blood plasma ($2.53 \pm 0.40\%$ vs. $1.55 \pm 0.29\%$, $P < 0.001$ and $25.18 \pm 2.15\%$ vs. $16.55 \pm 1.17\%$, $P < 0.001$, respectively), only the level of palmitoleic ($C_{16:1}$) acid is increased in erythrocytes ($0.56 \pm 0.12\%$ vs. $0.16 \pm 0.12\%$, $P < 0.001$). Despite the high content of oleic ($C_{18:1}$) acid in blood plasma in case of MODS, in erythrocytes its relative level is not changed as compared with the control group. The disorder of lipid composition constancy in erythrocyte membranes is also manifested by change in the content of saturated palmitic ($C_{16:0}$) and polyunsaturated linoleic ($C_{18:2}$) fatty

acids. In the test group of patients, as compared with the control group there was an elevated level ($27.12 \pm 0.78\%$ vs. $25.80 \pm 0.77\%$, $P < 0.05$) of saturated palmitic ($C_{16:0}$) acid combined with the reduced ($11.46 \pm 0.52\%$ vs. $13.95 \pm 1.09\%$, $P < 0.001$) level of linoleic ($C_{18:2}$) acid.

Conclusion The changes revealed in fatty acid composition of erythrocytes may indicate systemic modifications of cell membranes in MODS.

Reference

1. Kremmyda LS, et al. Biomed Pap Med Fac Univ Palacky Olomouc Czech Repub. 2011;155:195-218.

P26

Lower platelet mitochondrial function in severe septic patients than in controls

L Lorente¹, M Martin², J Blanquer³, J Solé-Violán⁴, L Labarta⁵, C Díaz⁶, A Jiménez¹, E López-Gallardo⁷, J Montoya⁷, E Ruiz-Pesini⁷
¹Hospital Universitario de Canarias, La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain; ²Hospital Universitario Nuestra Señora Candelaria, Santa Cruz, Tenerife, Spain; ³Hospital Clínico Universitario de Valencia, Spain; ⁴Hospital Universitario Dr Negrín, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain; ⁵Hospital San Jorge, Huesca, Spain; ⁶Hospital Insular, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain; ⁷Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain
Critical Care 2015, 19(Suppl 1):P26 (doi: 10.1186/cc14106)

Introduction The oxidative phosphorylation system (OXPHOS) in septic patients has been scarcely analyzed in studies of small sample size and the results are apparently inconsistent. Previously, including 96 severe septic patients, we found that nonsurviving severe septic patients showed lower platelet respiratory complex IV (CIV) activity than surviving patients at the moment of severe sepsis diagnosis and during the first week of sepsis diagnosis. However, we did not examine this enzyme activity in normal individuals. Thus, the objective of this study was to compare the CIV activity between severe septic patients and healthy control individuals in a larger series of patients (including 198 severe septic patients).

Methods This was a prospective, multicenter, observational study in six Spanish ICUs. We obtained blood samples from 198 severe septic patients at days 1, 4 and 8 of the severe sepsis diagnosis and from 96 sex-matched and age-matched healthy control individuals and determined platelet CIV activity/protein quantity. The endpoint of the study was 30-day mortality.

Results We found that severe septic patients showed lower CIV activity/protein quantity than controls at day 1 ($P < 0.001$), day 4 ($P < 0.001$) and day 8 ($P < 0.001$) of severe sepsis diagnosis. Survivor severe septic patients ($n = 130$) showed lower CIV activity/protein quantity than controls at day 1 ($P < 0.001$), day 4 ($P < 0.001$) and day 8 ($P < 0.001$) of severe sepsis diagnosis. In addition, nonsurvivor severe septic patients ($n = 68$) showed lower CIV activity/protein quantity than controls at day 1 ($P < 0.001$), day 4 ($P < 0.001$) and day 8 ($P < 0.001$) of severe sepsis diagnosis. Besides, nonsurvivor severe septic patients showed lower CIV activity/protein quantity than survivor ones at day 1 ($P < 0.001$), day 4 ($P < 0.001$) and day 8 ($P < 0.001$) of severe sepsis diagnosis.

Conclusion The major finding of our work, that represents the largest series of severe septic patients with data on OXPHOS function, was that survivor and nonsurvivor severe septic patients showed lower platelet CIV activity than healthy controls during the first week of severe sepsis diagnosis.

P27

Influence of genetic variants in the susceptibility and outcome of influenza virus infection

J Sole-Violán¹, M López-Rodríguez¹, E Herrera-Ramos¹, J Ruiz-Hernández¹, J Horcajada², L Borderías³, J Blanquer⁴, J Ferrer¹, O Rajas⁵, J Aspa⁵, F Rodríguez de Castro¹, C Rodríguez-Gallego¹

¹Hospital GC Dr Negrín, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain; ²Hospital del Mar, Barcelona, Spain; ³Hospital San Jorge, Huesca, Spain; ⁴Hospital Clínico, Valencia, Spain; ⁵Hospital de la Princesa, Madrid, Spain
Critical Care 2015, 19(Suppl 1):P27 (doi: 10.1186/cc14107)

Introduction The role of genetic variability in the susceptibility and outcome of influenza virus infection (IVI) remains largely unknown. We